

Dynamic approaches to Life Cycle Impact Assessment

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Dynamic GWP calculator (ALIGNED project)

► On this repository → <https://zenodo.org/records/11126481>

Check:

► [Tool for deriving dynamic characterization factors for climate change](#)

- This Excel spreadsheet contains an estimation of year-specific characterization factors (CF) for GWP100 (both Levasseur and Ventura methods), GWP500, GTP50 and GTP100, along with the calculation of characterized score for time-distributed CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O inventories. Instructions on how to use the score in real case LCA studies are also provided in the following tutorials.

► [See also the tutorials](#)

May 7, 2024 (1.1)

Project deliverable

Open

ALIGNED D1.2 Description of scientific methods (T1.3 Framework for Life Cycle Impact Assessment)

Hamelin, Lorie

Methods for Life Cycle Impact Assessment Help us improving the ALIGNED tools: please provide a feedback on your user experience, thank you! This repository contains: · Guide on the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) for bio-based products – Climate change This document...

Part of EU Open Research Repository

Uploaded on May 7, 2024

1 more versions exist for this record

 707

 1536

Concrete carbonation (Elliot et al., 2024)

► On this repository → <https://zenodo.org/records/13863452>

Check:

- dynamic LCA-based calculator for concrete blocks
 - to estimate the percentage of production impact mitigated by carbonation over 1000 years.
 - Unfortunately, values can not be exported :((mail the first author to get a copy with unlocked sheets)
- See also: full model and method published here: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.09.009>

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for a specific record. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. Below the navigation bar, the record details are displayed: 'Published September 30, 2024 | Version 2' and a 'Model' button with an 'Open' icon. The title of the record is 'Dynamic environmental payback of concrete due to carbonation over centuries'. The author is listed as 'Elliot, Thomas (Contact person)¹' with an ORCID icon and a 'Show affiliations' button. Under the 'Contributors' section, the 'Researchers:' list includes 'Elliot, Thomas', 'Kouchaki-Penchah, Hamed', 'Brial, Victor', and 'Levasseur, Annie', each with an ORCID icon. Below this, 'McLaren, Sarah¹' is listed with an ORCID icon and another 'Show affiliations' button.

Exercise

- Take the building case study, choose one building
- Find out the amount of concrete used.
- Use the amount of carbonation reported in Elliot et al. as rough approximation. $0.06 \text{ kg CO}_2 / \text{kg concrete}$ in service life of building (100 year)
- Use the dynamic GWP calculator to obtain the corresponding GWP (assume a linear carbonation over the period)
- Modify the LCA of building by adding this amount and recalculate results.